

CLOSED-LOOP SPINAL STIMULATION FOR PHASE-LOCKED MODULATION OF PATHOLOGICAL TREMOR

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ABSTRACT

1 Essential tremor (ET) is the most prevalent movement disorder, yet existing pharmacological and
2 surgical treatments often lack efficacy or involve significant risks. Phase-locked neuromodulation
3 offers a targeted approach to disrupt pathological oscillations, but its implementation through non-
4 invasive spinal cord stimulation (tSCS) has remained largely unexplored. In this study, we present a
5 novel closed-loop tSCS framework for ET based on real-time tremor phase estimation from surface
6 electromyography (EMG). The system implements a Fourier Linear Combiner (FLC) algorithm to
7 track the demodulated EMG signal sample-by-sample, enabling short-latency stimulation delivery
8 while mitigating the phase lag inherent in traditional filtering or decomposition methods. The
9 framework was validated in ET patients performing an isometric precision pinching task, with
10 stimulation delivered across eight equidistant phases of the tremor cycle. The results demonstrate the
11 technical feasibility of the system, which achieved a peak-to-trough tremor amplitude modulation
12 of approximately 20% relative to the trial mean. Furthermore, the observation of phase-dependent
13 frequency modulation in a subset of participants suggested that tSCS can interact with central
14 tremorgenic oscillators via spinal afferent pathways without compromising voluntary motor control.
15 These findings provide an initial demonstration that closed-loop tSCS can produce phase-dependent
16 modulation of tremor in individual patients, where therapeutic efficacy is driven by the precise
17 temporal synchronization of stimuli with the patient's underlying neurophysiology.

18 **Keywords** Closed-loop · Essential tremor · Non-invasive stimulation · Spinal cord · TSCS

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1 Introduction

Essential Tremor (ET) is the most prevalent movement disorder worldwide, affecting approximately 5% of the population over 65 years of age [1]. Clinically defined by a persistent action tremor of the upper limbs in the absence of other neurological signs [2], ET significantly impairs functional independence and social participation [3]. Despite its prevalence, the pathophysiology of ET remains incompletely understood and is increasingly viewed as a heterogeneous syndrome with diverse etiologies and not yet fully defined phenotypes, currently classified as ET plus [4, 5]. This complexity is reflected by the limited efficacy of pharmacological treatments, which are often hindered by adverse effects or partial relief [6, 7]. Therefore, there is a clinical demand for alternative therapeutic strategies that can provide effective symptom management while avoiding the limitations of current treatments.

Neuromodulation has emerged as a key strategy to treat ET by disrupting the aberrant tremorgenic activity within the cerebello-thalamo-cortical (CTC) loop [8, 9]. Current neuromodulation approaches can be broadly categorized into central and peripheral interventions [10]. Central interventions, primarily Deep Brain Stimulation (DBS), have provided encouraging results in terms of tremor modulation [11]. However, the invasiveness of these approaches, together with the technical complexity and long-term habituation effects represent significant barriers [12, 13]. Conversely, peripheral neuromodulation, such as afferent stimulation, offers a safer and simpler non-invasive alternative [14]. Yet, these peripheral approaches often fail to interact directly with the central nervous system (CNS) oscillators and lead to variable results across subjects [15]. Consequently, there is a need for novel non-invasive interfaces capable of effectively targeting the central oscillatory circuits.

The spinal cord represents a compelling and strategically positioned entry point for neuromodulation interventions targeting central tremors. As an integral component of the CNS, the spinal cord serves as a direct interface between supraspinal oscillators and peripheral outputs [16]. Although it is not directly involved in the generation of tremors, it is far from being a passive relay as it can critically amplify or act as a resonance chamber of the descending tremorgenic drive to the muscles [17, 18]. Transcutaneous spinal cord stimulation (tSCS) is a non-invasive form of spinal stimulation that has received increasing attention as a non-invasive tool to modulate the neural activity in spinal circuits. The potential of tSCS as a neuromodulatory option has been demonstrated across diverse applications, from restoring motor function in spinal cord injury [19] to modulating spinal excitability and gait in healthy individuals [20], and patients affected by orthostatic tremor [21]. In the context of ET, previous studies have shown that tSCS may modulate tremor severity, although the magnitude of the effect was relatively moderate and variable [22].

So far, the effects of tSCS on tremor have been assessed using open-loop stimulation paradigms, which entail delivering electrical stimuli at tremor frequency but with uncontrolled relationship between the stimulus and the ongoing tremor phase. Studies using different types of neuromodulation have shown that effects can be substantially strengthened when the stimulus phase is temporally linked with the targeted neural activity [23, 24]. Therefore, a potential way to reinforce the neuromodulatory effects of tSCS on pathological tremors may be to identify the optimal phase relationship between the stimulus and the ongoing tremor, and to use it to stimulate the spinal cord circuits in closed-loop with the measured tremor activity.

In this work, we propose a novel closed-loop framework for tSCS designed to modulate pathological oscillations by targeting the instantaneous tremor phase. Our approach leverages surface electromyography (EMG) as a direct surrogate of the central tremorgenic drive [17], allowing for a sample-by-sample phase estimation that minimizes filter-induced latencies. We implemented an innovative protocol where stimulation was delivered at different tremor phases during a task involving sustained contractions (Figure 1A). The primary objective of this study is to characterize the phase-dependency of tremor amplitude modulation using tSCS. We hypothesize that spinal afferent recruitment can dynamically interact with central tremor rhythms, where the timing of the stimulation pulses relative to the tremor cycle dictates the nature of the interaction. Specifically, alignment with the optimal phase is expected to produce destructive interference, decreasing the oscillatory output; whereas stimulation at the anti-optimal phase may result in constructive interference, potentially exacerbating tremor. This phase-locked interaction is thus predicted to manifest as a continuous sinusoidal modulation of tremor intensity. By combining the non-invasiveness of tSCS with the temporal precision of closed-loop control, we aim to better understand the underlying mechanisms of pathological tremor and open new avenues for therapeutic intervention leveraging spinal neuromodulation.

2 Methods

2.1 Participants

Fourteen participants (mean age, 66.7 ± 3.9 years; 8 females) diagnosed with ET were recruited from the neurology unit of Hospital 12 de Octubre, Madrid, Spain. Patients with neurological disorders other than ET, implantable electronic devices (such as pacemakers or neurostimulators), or dermatological alterations in the stimulation area were excluded.

Figure 1: Experimental setup, task, and closed-loop stimulation procedure. **(A)** Schematic of the closed-loop system combining surface EMG recording, online phase estimation, and transcutaneous spinal cord stimulation (tSCS). **(B)** Precision isometric pinching task with visual force-tracking feedback at 10% of MVC. **(C)** Signal processing pipeline: EMG is rectified and processed through the adaptive filter. Then, instantaneous phase is extracted in real time, and stimulation pulses are delivered accordingly. **(D,E)** Representative examples of EMG traces during stimulation at two different phases of the tremor cycle. **(F)** Example of a complete task run: each target phase color represents a stimulation phase condition, while the colored dots indicate the real phase of the delivered stimulation pulses. The gray background denotes open-loop stimulation periods (first 30 seconds, and in this particular block, the second-to-last interval, from 65 to 70 seconds).

72 Participants were excluded if their tremor was too mild or intermittent to allow for reliable measurement (determined by
 73 the presence of a distinct EMG spectral peak between 3 and 8 Hz), or if they were unable to sustain the required pinching
 74 posture for the necessary duration. All participants took part in a single experimental session lasting approximately
 75 two hours. To minimize the effects of medication, they were instructed not to take their usual tremor medication on
 76 the evening prior to the session. The study was approved by the Ethics Committee for Research with Medicines at the
 77 Hospital Universitario "12 de Octubre" (protocol number 24/050, February 2024) and was performed in accordance
 78 with the Declaration of Helsinki. All participants signed an informed consent form before inclusion. More information
 79 about study participants can be found in Table 1.

Table 1: Demographic and clinical characteristics of participants, along with stimulation parameters. DD: Disease Duration. ST: Side Tested. F_T : Tremor Frequency. MT: motor threshold. SI: Stimulation Intensity. P: Propranolol. Pi: Primidone. Z: Zonisamide.

ID	Age (y)	Gender	DD (y)	Medication	ST	F_T (Hz)	MT (mA)	SI (mA)
ET01	56-60	F	9	P	R	5.7	32.0	29.0
ET02	61-65	M	8	-	R	6.0	45.0	40.0
ET03	66-70	M	-	P, Pi	L	5.8	23.0	20.0
ET04	76-80	F	27	-	R	5.2	31.0	27.9
ET05	66-70	M	14	P	R	5.7	51.0	45.9
ET06	61-65	F	8	-	L	5.5	35.0	32.5
ET07	66-70	F	10	P	L	5.5	40.0	36.0
ET08	61-65	F	15	P	R	5.9	40.0	36.0
ET09	66-70	F	9	P	R	5.8	41.0	37.0
ET10	61-65	F	7	Pi	R	5.2	40.0	36.0
ET11	66-70	F	8	P, Pi	L	5.7	39.0	35.1
ET12	61-65	M	26	Pi	L	4.9	42.0	37.8
ET13	66-70	M	13	Pi, Z	R	5.7	37.0	33.3
ET14	66-70	M	18	P	R	5.3	49.0	44.0
M \pm SD	66.7 \pm 3.9	-	13.2 \pm 6.7		-	5.6 \pm 0.3	38.9 \pm 7.3	35.0 \pm 6.6

80 2.2 Experimental design

81 At the beginning of the experimental sessions, participants were asked to perform a palmar pinching task, holding
 82 a force sensor between the index finger and the thumb (Figure 1B), and their maximum voluntary contraction force
 83 (MVC) was recorded. This task was selected both for its functional relevance to activities of daily living and to ensure
 84 a stable phase relationship between the surface EMG and the neural tremorgenic drive, since isometric contractions
 85 provide relatively constant afferent contributions to the spinal motor neuron pool [17]. Afterwards, they sustained an
 86 isometric force level of 10% MVC with visual feedback for one minute to estimate their dominant tremor frequency.
 87 Tremor frequency (F_T) was identified as the peak power in the EMG (3–8 Hz) using the Welch method (2 s window,
 88 50% overlap, 0.1 Hz resolution). This window length balances spectral resolution and signal stationarity, ensuring at
 89 least six cycles are captured at the lowest frequency (3 Hz).

90 Then, subjects performed several blocks of the precision pinching isometric task with visual feedback of the applied
 91 force, resting for at least one minute between them. Each block had a total duration of 75 seconds and included an
 92 initial ramp of 5 seconds, during which the force progressively increased from rest to a target of 10% MVC. Subjects
 93 held that level of force for the rest of the block while tSCS was delivered at different phases of the tremor.

94 In the first 30 seconds of the block, stimulation was delivered in open-loop (OL) mode, adjusted to the previously
 95 estimated tremor dominant frequency. This interval was chosen in line with recent reports [22] indicating that the
 96 efficacy of tSCS tends to increase after 30 seconds, possibly due to the interaction with additional neural circuits, while
 97 also minimizing initial transient effects associated with stimulation onset. Subsequently, eight 5-second closed-loop
 98 stimulations were applied, in which the phase of the stimulation was synchronized with the EMG activity of the
 99 FDI muscle (Figure 1C), covering eight equispaced phase conditions (Figures 1D & 1E). An additional 5-second OL
 100 condition was included within these blocks. The nine conditions were applied in pseudorandom order in each block
 101 (Figure 1F). The 5-second epochs were designed to capture immediate modulatory effects while mitigating tremor
 102 non-stationarity. By cycling through all phases within a 45-second window, following the initial 30-second stabilization,
 103 we ensured robustness against spontaneous drifts in tremor intensity. This structure allowed for comprehensive
 104 phase-response mapping while minimizing patient fatigue and ensuring stable task performance.

105 Each participant performed 10 repetitions of these stimulation blocks. Three additional blocks without stimulation were
 106 also recorded: at the beginning, in the middle (after the fifth repetition), and at the end, which served as a reference

107 to obtain baseline measurements and control for possible effects of time or performance improvements due to task
 108 learning.

109 2.3 Recordings and stimulation

110 Bipolar surface electromyography (EMG) signals were acquired at 2000 Hz from the *first dorsal interosseous* (FDI)
 111 using an embedded system (*EAST, OT Bioelettronica*, IT) with biosignal amplification and online processing capabilities.
 112 The compact size of the bipolar electrodes allowed for the additional placement of a 64-electrode high-density surface
 113 electromyography (HDsEMG) grid (13x5 array, 4 mm pitch) adjacently on the same FDI muscle. Force signal was
 114 also recorded with a load transducer placed between the index finger and the thumb. HDsEMG and the force signal
 115 were sampled at 2048 Hz and digitized using a multichannel acquisition system (*Quattrocento, OT Bioelettronica*, IT),
 116 synchronized with the stimulation system via an acquisition card (*Micro1401, Cambridge Electronic Design*, UK).

117 An electrical stimulator (DS8R, Digitimer Ltd., United Kingdom) was used to deliver tSCS. A 90 x 50 mm anodic
 118 electrode was placed on the posterior neck region at the level of C6, and a 50 x 90 mm cathodic electrode was placed on
 119 the clavicle of the side with the most tremor of the patient. The stimulation protocol consisted of 1 ms pulses with a
 120 carrier frequency of 5 kHz, resulting in five 200 μ s biphasic pulses [22]. The stimulation intensity was determined for
 121 each subject as 90% of their motor threshold. For this purpose, an intensity of 5 mA was initiated and increased until
 122 the appearance of an evoked muscle response in 50% of the pulses in the EMG signal. In instances where an evoked
 123 motor response was not initially observed, electrodes were slightly repositioned to optimize neural targeting. If the
 124 motor threshold could not be successfully determined after repeated adjustments, the experimental intensity was instead
 125 defined by the participant's self-reported discomfort threshold.

126 2.4 Phase-tracking algorithm

127 Muscle activity estimated via EMG is supposed to maintain a stable phase relation with the central tremor generator
 128 [17]. Thus, we used the EMG from the FDI to estimate the phase of the tremor-related activity, employing an adaptive
 129 filter based on a sinusoidal model (Fourier Linear Combiner, FLC, Figure 2A) implemented in real time on the EAST
 130 system (32-bit ARM Cortex M4 microprocessor).

131 Our implementation utilizes the rectified EMG signal ($x(n)$) as the input source. The signal was downsampled and
 132 processed at 1000 Hz, which reduced redundancy while preserving the frequency content of interest in the tremor
 133 band. The signal $\hat{x}(n)$ was then modeled as a linear combination of a sine and a cosine at the tremor frequency (F_T ,
 134 previously determined), along with a DC component. The resulting estimate signal was:

$$\hat{x}(n) = w_1(n) \cdot \sin(\theta(n)) + w_2(n) \cdot \cos(\theta(n)) + w_3(n) \quad (1)$$

135 where $\theta(n) = 2\pi \cdot \frac{F_T}{f_s} \cdot n$. The weights $w_1(n)$, $w_2(n)$, and $w_3(n)$ are initialized at zero at the start of the block and
 136 then updated online, sample by sample, using the least-mean-squares (LMS) algorithm:

$$w_1(n+1) = w_1(n) + \mu_1 \cdot e(n) \cdot \sin(\theta(n)) \quad (2)$$

$$w_2(n+1) = w_2(n) + \mu_2 \cdot e(n) \cdot \cos(\theta(n)) \quad (3)$$

$$w_3(n+1) = w_3(n) + \mu_3 \cdot e(n) \quad (4)$$

137 to minimize the mean square error (MSE), where $e(n)$ represents the estimation error:

$$e(n) = x(n) - \hat{x}(n) \quad (5)$$

138 Based on offline tests, the adaptive coefficients μ_1 and μ_2 were equal to 2^{-6} , whereas μ_3 was set to 2^{-8} . These values
 139 ensured that the algorithm could adapt rapidly enough to capture changes in both the amplitude and phase of the tremor
 140 while remaining robust against the influence of high-frequency EMG components (Figure 2B). The phase of the tremor
 141 signal was then extracted from the sinusoidal weights:

$$\phi(n) = \theta(n) + \arg(w_1(n) + jw_2(n)) \quad (6)$$

142 Each stimulation pulse was delivered when the absolute difference between the estimated phase and the target phase
 143 was less than $\pi/12$ radians, while also incorporating a mandatory refractory period of one-fourth of the tremor period
 144 to ensure that only a single stimulation pulse was delivered per period.

145 This formulation allowed for continuous tracking of the tremor phase and amplitude with minimal computational
 146 overhead, suitable for real-time embedded implementations.

Figure 2: Architecture and performance of the Fourier Linear Combiner (FLC) for tremor envelope estimation. (A) Block diagram of the adaptive algorithm. A reference signal, generated at the estimated tremor frequency (F_T), is decomposed into orthogonal components weighted by adaptive coefficients (w_1, w_2) and a bias term (w_3). The weights are updated adaptively using the Least Mean Squares (LMS) algorithm with a learning rate vector μ to minimize the mean squared value of the estimated error ($e(n)$). The output $\hat{x}(n)$ represents the adaptive estimate of the oscillatory tremor component, derived continuously from the extracted EMG envelope. (B) Time-domain tracking performance. Comparison of the online FLC estimation ($\hat{x}(n)$, blue line) against a "ground truth" envelope obtained via offline zero-phase filtering (dark gray line). The background gray signal shows the noisy EMG input. The close overlap demonstrates the proposed algorithm's ability to accurately track the tremor envelope in real-time with minimal phase lag compared to the offline benchmark. (C) Polar histogram showing the distribution of actual delivered phases relative to the desired stimulation phase across all pulses and subjects. Mean and standard deviation are provided for each condition. (D) Tremor frequency stability analysis. Subject-wise comparison of the instantaneous tremor frequency distribution during No Stimulation (brown) and all Stimulation (blue) conditions. The central mark in each box indicates the median frequency, while the box edges represent the interquartile range (25th–75th percentiles). The consistent frequency overlap between conditions confirms that the intervention does not alter tremor's fundamental rhythm, and validates the FLC's ability to track frequency shifts robustly.

147 2.5 Data analysis and Statistics

148 To assess the accuracy of the online phase estimation algorithm, the EMG signal was rectified and band-pass filtered
 149 around the individual tremor frequency ($F_T \pm 1.5Hz$) using a zero-phase second-order Butterworth filter. The analytic
 150 signal was first constructed using the Hilbert transform. From this complex representation, the instantaneous phase
 151 was obtained as the angle (argument) of the signal. The performance of the algorithm was evaluated by extracting the
 152 instantaneous phase at the time points marked by the stimulation triggers, providing a direct measure of whether the
 153 pulses had been delivered at the intended phase of the tremor cycle. For each stimulation condition, we computed the
 154 circular mean, circular standard deviation, and Phase Locking Value (PLV) [25]:

$$PLV = \frac{1}{N} \left| \sum_{i=1}^N e^{j(\phi_d - \phi_i)} \right| \quad (7)$$

155 Where ϕ_d is the target phase and ϕ_i refers to the actual phase in which each stimulation pulse was delivered. This
 156 metric was also calculated in the open-loop periods to assess if tSCS could entrain ongoing tremors, with a significance
 157 threshold of 0.15. Lastly, the sensitivity index (d') [26] was computed to measure the separability between adjacent
 158 phase conditions.

159 To quantify tremor severity, the force signal was filtered (2nd order Butterworth bandpass, $F_T \pm 1.5Hz$), and the
 160 instantaneous amplitude was then computed as the magnitude (envelope) of the analytic signal (Figure 4A). To determine
 161 whether stimulation induced a generic, phase-independent response, we assessed the overall impact of stimulation on
 162 tremor amplitude and frequency by comparing the pooled responses across all participants and stimulation phases in the
 163 stimulation blocks against the no-stimulation baseline using Wilcoxon signed-rank tests.

164 The analysis of subject-specific responsiveness to phase-locked stimulation was conducted using one-second data
 165 windows [22, 24]. To quantify amplitude modulation, the instantaneous tremor amplitude was averaged within each
 166 one-second segment and subsequently normalized to the mean of the entire block. This procedure mitigated the
 167 influence of baseline fluctuations and isolated the relative change in tremor intensity for each stimulation phase within
 168 blocks. In parallel, the tremor frequency for each segment was estimated by unwrapping the instantaneous phase and
 169 calculating the average slope of the phase progression, defined as the difference between the final and initial phase
 170 values divided by the segment duration. The following statistical analysis was performed. Since we expected a periodic
 171 phase-dependent modulation pattern, resulting from constructive and destructive interference with the underlying tremor
 172 drive, individual response profiles for amplitude and frequency were modeled using a sinusoidal function of the form

$$y = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \cos(\theta_i + \beta_2) \quad (8)$$

173 where θ_i denotes each stimulation phase, β_0 the baseline level, β_1 the modulation depth, and β_2 the phase offset.
 174 Outliers outside a range of 1.5 IQR were removed for this analysis. To evaluate phase-dependency, we calculated an
 175 F -statistic by comparing the sinusoidal fit against a null hypothesis of a constant mean response. This observed F -value
 176 served as the test statistic for a non-parametric permutation procedure (10^4 iterations per subject). In each iteration,
 177 stimulation phase labels (θ_i) were randomly shuffled to generate a surrogate distribution representing the absence of
 178 phase modulation. For each surrogate dataset, the sinusoidal model was re-fitted and a new F -statistic was computed.
 179 The empirical p -value was then defined as the proportion of surrogate F -statistics that exceeded the observed F -statistic
 180 from the original data, with a significance threshold of $p < 0.05$.

181 Finally, to elucidate the determinants of the observed inter-subject variability and identify potential predictors of
 182 therapeutic efficacy, we performed a *post hoc* exploratory analysis. Following the classification of the cohort into
 183 responders (those presenting a statistically significant sinusoidal tremor amplitude modulation profile, $p < 0.05$) and
 184 non-responders, we investigated the relationship between the stimulation effect size (and its statistical significance) and
 185 a comprehensive set of subject-specific covariates. These were categorized into four domains: demographic factors (e.g.,
 186 age, gender), clinical treatment profiles (medication), experimental parameters (e.g., motor thresholds), and baseline
 187 tremor characteristics (amplitude, frequency, and the variability of both).

188 3 Results

189 3.1 Robust real-time tremor tracking enables precise phase-locked stimulation

190 The phase-tracking algorithm demonstrated robust performance across the eight stimulation conditions. Stimulation
 191 triggers were tightly locked to the intended phase, with a mean PLV of 0.865 ± 0.014 . The mean delivered phase angle
 192 for each condition closely matched the theoretical target (mean error -9.62°), with limited within-subject variability.
 193 This value can be explained by the inclusion of a tolerance window of 15° around the desired phase, so stimulation
 194 was triggered when the estimated phase crossed the lower threshold of the window. Importantly, adjacent conditions
 195 were well separated, as reflected by d' values (3.85 ± 0.91 standard deviations across conditions), confirming reliable
 196 discrimination between neighboring phases. Together, these metrics demonstrate the accuracy of the closed-loop system
 197 in delivering stimulation at the desired phase of tremor-related EMG activity (Figure 2C).

Figure 3: Tremor entrainment in open-loop stimulation. Polar histograms of stimulation pulse timings relative to the ongoing tremor phase during open-loop intervals for each subject, illustrating the distribution of phase-locking and potential entrainment effects.

198 **3.2 Stimulation preserves global tremor characteristics**

199 TSCS was well tolerated by all participants, with no adverse events or discomfort reported beyond a mild tapping
 200 sensation. Stimulation intensities were individualized based on motor thresholds (38.9 ± 7.3 mA), with slight inter-
 201 individual variability in electrode positioning. Moreover, the application of tSCS did not induce a generalized,
 202 non-specific disruption of the tremor. When pooling all stimulation conditions, no significant global changes in tremor
 203 frequency (Wilcoxon test for paired samples, $N = 14$, $p = 0.21$, Figure 1D) or amplitude ($p = 0.17$) were observed
 204 compared to baseline. This preservation of baseline characteristics at the group level suggests that the observed effects
 205 are likely specific to the phase of delivery rather than a generic response to electrical current.

206 The afferent and sub-threshold nature of the intervention was confirmed by the absence of consistent motor evoked
 207 potentials (MEPs) following stimulation pulses (see Supplementary Materials). Furthermore, we verified that stimulation
 208 artifacts did not bias the phase estimation. Although a residual artifact was visible in the average response of some
 209 participants, the low PLV observed during open-loop stimulation (0.08 ± 0.06) confirms the integrity of the closed-loop
 210 tracking; a significant coupling between the artifact and the phase estimation would have resulted in artificially inflated
 211 PLV levels, which was not the case.

212 **3.3 Phase-dependent modulation of tremor dynamics**

213 To evaluate the capacity of tSCS to interact with the central tremor generator, we first analyzed the open-loop condition.
 214 During non-phase-locked stimulation, we observed remarkably low entrainment levels (mean PLV 0.08 ± 0.06 , Figure
 215 3, only 2 patients displayed significant entrainment values during open-loop stimulation), with polar plots showing a
 216 uniform distribution of stimulation phases without significant alignment. This confirmed that, in the absence of real-time
 217 synchronization, tSCS failed to achieve a stable interaction with the tremorgenic rhythm, justifying the necessity of a
 218 closed-loop approach.

219 To quantify phase-dependent effects, we examined whether tSCS could induce sinusoidal fluctuations in tremor features
 220 through interference patterns. This approach assumes that the tremorgenic signal is susceptible to phase-specific
 221 dampening (at the optimal timing) or exacerbation (at the anti-optimal timing). The adequacy of this sinusoidal model
 222 thus reflects the degree of stable interaction between spinal afferent recruitment and central tremor descending output.

223 Regarding tremor amplitude, an initial examination in the absolute phase space revealed that tSCS-induced effects were
 224 obscured by high inter-subject variability, with no single phase producing a uniform response across the cohort (Figure
 225 4C). However, a systematic group-level modulation profile was unveiled when individual responses were aligned to
 226 each participant's optimal suppressive phase (relative-phase space, Figure 4D), where the optimal phase achieved a
 227 mean reduction of $20.84\% \pm 9.47\%$. At the individual level, 6 out of 14 subjects (43%) exhibited significant sinusoidal
 228 modulation. For these responders, optimal phase stimulation suppressed tremor by $30.24\% \pm 11.21\%$ relative to
 229 open-loop, while the anti-optimal phase increased it by $11.36\% \pm 13.45\%$ (Figure 4E). Notably, the remaining subjects
 230 showed no evidence of phase-dependent effects following a sinusoidal trajectory.

231 In parallel, we examined whether tSCS could induce consistent shifts in tremor frequency across the cohort. We
 232 conducted a similar analytical approach. However, unlike the amplitude results, no uniform sinusoidal modulation
 233 emerged at the group level (Figure 5B), even when data were aligned in relative-phase space (Figure 5C). This suggests
 234 that frequency entrainment is not a generalized response to the stimulation parameters employed. Tremor frequency was
 235 susceptible to phase-locked modulation in a subset of the cohort (4 out of 14 subjects), displaying a distinct sinusoidal
 236 profile (Figure 5D). Interestingly, this frequency modulation appeared largely dissociated from the amplitude changes:
 237 only one participant (ET07) showed significant modulation in both metrics. Although the possibility of false positives
 238 cannot be fully excluded, the use of rigorous statistical surrogates minimizes this risk, suggesting that the observed
 239 dissociation is physiological. This implies that the mechanisms controlling the pacing of the central oscillator may
 240 function independently of those governing the recruitment of the motor units [27]. More explicitly, this points to
 241 a physiological decoupling between the modulation of tremor magnitude and its rhythmic pacing, suggesting that
 242 phase-locked tSCS can selectively target either the timing or the intensity of the tremor through distinct neural pathways.

243 Finally, we investigated whether subject-specific characteristics could predict these diverse responses. Correlation
 244 analysis across demographics, medication, baseline tremor features, and experimental measures revealed no statistically
 245 significant predictors ($p > 0.05$ for all comparisons with tremor amplitude response, Figure 6). The lack of distinct
 246 clustering among responders suggests that the efficacy of phase-locked tSCS is not dictated by macroscopic clinical phe-
 247 notypes, but rather by individualized neurophysiological dynamics, such as the specific nerve anatomy and connectivity
 248 of each patient; or experimental stochasticity, including inter-subject variability in electrode-to-target geometry.

249 4 Discussion

250 In this study, we tested the effects of closed-loop tSCS on ET. By locking stimulation to the ongoing tremor phase
 251 derived from surface EMG, we show that it is possible to induce systematic phase-dependent changes in the tremor
 252 amplitude in a subset of patients with ET. These findings add to the growing body of approaches for phase-specific
 253 tremor modulation. A main novelty of our approach is the stimulation modality for closed loop neuromodulation:
 254 instead of directly stimulating the brain [23, 24] or stimulating afferent nerve fibers through muscle stimulation [28],
 255 we used tSCS, which is expected to target the spinal cord circuitry at a specific level. Our findings suggest that tSCS
 256 provides a non-invasive interface to engage the neural circuits associated with tremor through spinal afferent pathways.
 257 Even though the modulation confirms an interaction with the tremorgenic drive at the spinal level, the extent to which
 258 this reflects a direct influence on central oscillators remains to be further elucidated.

259 The phase-locked approach implemented in this study achieved a peak-to-trough amplitude modulation of approximately
 260 20% relative to the trial mean, an effect size that, while not translating into an absolute reduction compared to non-
 261 stimulation periods in our cohort, remains comparable to other non-invasive modalities such as cerebellar tACS (21.5%
 262 [24]) and below the benchmarks of invasive DBS (37.5% [23]). It is important to emphasize that our experimental
 263 design was exclusively focused on characterizing instantaneous phase-dependent effects rather than replicating the
 264 sustained, absolute suppression reported in previous open-loop studies [22]. A critical methodological factor in this
 265 regard is the duration of our stimulation windows; the use of relatively short blocks may have precluded the temporal
 266 integration required for cumulative phase-unspecific inhibitory effects to manifest. This may explain why, despite
 267 both studies showed a similar tremor amplitude change during the first 30 seconds of tSCS delivered in open loop, the
 268 subsequent tremor dynamics differ significantly. Specifically, in the previous work based on open loop stimulation a
 269 trend towards decreased tremor amplitude across time was reported, suggesting a build up effect of the stimulation
 270 on tremor reduction. On the contrary, our results showed that tremor amplitude remained higher during stimulation
 271 blocks than in baseline blocks (without tSCS). This discrepancy may be attributed to the structure of our closed-loop
 272 protocol, where the inclusion of stimulation at phases that can have diverging effects on the tremor amplitude may
 273 mask cumulative effects observed during open loop tSCS. Consequently, the extent to which the phase-specific effects
 274 observed here might interact with the inherent inhibitory potential of tSCS remains to be elucidated, and whether the
 275 mechanisms observed in open-loop and closed-loop paradigms are additive is a question for future research requiring
 276 dedicated protocols focused on prolonged stimulation at a single, subject-specific optimal phase. At this stage, our
 277 results serve as a characterization of the system's modulatory capacity.

278 A similar logic applies to the lack of significant frequency entrainment during open-loop stimulation in our cohort. In
 279 [22], entrainment was primarily observed in subjects with high tremor suppression during long, continuous 1-minute
 280 windows, suggesting that a reduced tremor amplitude may facilitate the pacing of the central oscillator. In contrast,
 281 our analysis relied on multiple shorter blocks, each starting at a stochastic (random) tremor phase. These shorter
 282 intervals may not provide sufficient time for the neural oscillator to stabilize or "lock" to the external stimulus before the
 283 block ends. Consequently, the averaging of these non-stabilized segments likely leads to a poorer entrainment profile
 284 compared to the long-duration, continuous paradigms used in previous research.

Figure 4: Analysis of phase-dependent modulation of tremor amplitude. (A) Signal processing methodology for amplitude estimation. Representative traces showing the raw force signal (red), the band-pass filtered component centered at the individual tremor frequency ($f_t \pm 1.5$ Hz, black), and the instantaneous amplitude envelope extracted via the Hilbert transform (dark red). The mean amplitude was computed during the stimulation window to quantify modulation. (B) Temporal dynamics of tremor amplitude across the cohort. The plot displays the group-averaged tremor envelope (solid lines) over time for the No-Stimulation (brown) and Stimulation (blue). Shaded regions represent the Standard Error of the Mean (SEM) across all subjects ($N = 14$). Time $t = 0$ denotes the onset of the stimulation period. A progressive increase in tremor amplitude is seen in both groups as they start the task. (C) Group-level distribution of tremor amplitude across the eight targeted stimulation phases (absolute phase). Boxplots indicate the median and interquartile ranges, with individual data points representing the mean response of each subject. Data from the open-loop stimulation condition are shown in gray. (D) Same as C, but individual profiles were aligned to the optimal suppressive phase (defined as 0°). (E) Individual response profiles. Normalized tremor amplitude computed over 1-s analysis windows (dots) versus the stimulation phase. Purple lines represent the best-fit sinusoidal function, with significance (p -value) indicated for each subject. 10

Figure 5: **Analysis of phase-dependent modulation of tremor frequency.** (A) Signal processing methodology for instant tremor frequency estimation. (B) Group-level distribution of tremor frequency across the eight targeted stimulation phases (absolute phase). Boxplots indicate the median and interquartile ranges, with individual data points representing the mean response of each subject. Data from the open-loop stimulation condition are shown in gray. (C) Same as B, but individual profiles were aligned to the optimal suppressive phase (defined as 0°). (D) Subject-level changes in tremor frequency during stimulation, shown as boxplots with individual trial data points overlaid. Dashed lines indicate individual tremor frequency estimated from the baseline period. Red lines represent the best-fit sinusoidal function, with significance (p -value) indicated for each subject.

Figure 6: **Exploratory analysis of determinants of stimulation efficacy.** The figure displays the relationship between the stimulation outcome ($-\log_{10}(p\text{-value})$ of sinusoidal fit) and various subject-specific characteristics. Scatter plots represent continuous variables (e.g., Age, Disease Duration, Motor Threshold, Tremor Amplitude). No significant relationship (linear or clustering) was found between these variables and the outcome of the experiment. Boxplots illustrate the distribution of the stimulation effect across categorical subgroups, (Medication and Gender. The central mark indicates the median, and the box edges represent the 25th and 75th percentiles. No significant differences were observed between gender or medication subgroups.

285 While peripheral strategies such as FES or reciprocal inhibition can achieve substantial amplitude reductions (from
 286 32% to 58% [28]), their effects are primarily limited to single muscle mechanics and are often restricted by fatigue. In
 287 contrast, our phase-locked tSCS achieved a more moderate reduction; yet it provided evidence of interaction with the
 288 central tremorigenic drive under certain conditions. Specifically, the sinusoidal frequency modulation observed in a
 289 subset of four subjects suggests that the intervention may influence the timing of the central oscillator. Although this
 290 effect was not universal across our cohort, these cases provide a technical proof-of-concept for the spinal cord as a
 291 functional gateway to the motor network. Importantly, this central interaction appears to be highly selective; recent
 292 evidence indicates that tSCS does not compromise voluntary motor control or functional performance [29].

293 Clinically, the results show the potential of spinal stimulation to modulate tremor oscillations in a personalized fashion,
 294 adjusting stimulation timing to the intrinsic oscillatory dynamics of each individual. This positions tSCS as a promising
 295 candidate for future therapeutic applications in ET, with advantages such as non-invasiveness, adaptability, and
 296 usability during activities of daily living. Furthermore, the identification of phase-sensitive windows provides a novel
 297 programmable dimension for the optimization of invasive spinal cord stimulation (SCS) therapies. By incorporating
 298 timing as a tunable parameter, these findings align with established paradigms in spatio-temporal neuromodulation,
 299 where precisely timed spinal stimulation is used to leverage the natural dynamics of motor circuits to maximize
 300 functional outcomes [30]. More broadly, the findings extend the principle of phase-specific neuromodulation beyond
 301 the brain, suggesting that the spinal cord may serve as an effective target for temporally-precise interventions.

302 We used the extracted EMG envelope as a surrogate of the neural tremorigenic drive that is being targeted by the
 303 stimulation, assuming a stable phase relationship between them. This assumption is expected to be adequate during
 304 isometric muscle contractions, where the relative contributions of the afferences from different muscles to spinal motor
 305 neuron inputs remain relatively stable [31, 32, 33, 17]. However, changes in the level of activation of different muscles
 306 in a limb could cause changes in the balance of the tremorigenic inputs to different motor neuron pools [17]. This may
 307 imply that the optimal phases between the applied tSCS and the sensed tremor in the measured muscle change over
 308 time. Further work is needed to investigate optimal ways to dynamically adapt the tremor-stimulus phase alignment to
 309 optimize the stimulation effects in terms of tremor suppression.

310 The distinction between responders and non-responders in our cohort highlights a fundamental challenge in tremor
 311 neuromodulation. The fact that standard clinical markers failed to predict efficacy suggests that the therapeutic window
 312 for tSCS is not governed by the patient’s macro-phenotype, but rather by the individualized neurophysiological coupling
 313 between the electrical field and the specific neural architecture of each subject. This lack of clinical predictors, also
 314 reported in DBS [23], tACS [24], and open-loop tSCS [22], implies that phase-locked effects are highly sensitive to
 315 both the specific topology of tremorigenic circuits and the dynamic nature of the tremor itself. Consequently, this
 316 variability should not be interpreted as a limitation of the stimulation method, but as evidence that successful modulation
 317 depends on a precise alignment with the patient’s intrinsic neurophysiological state. Even subtle anatomical variations
 318 in afferent pathways or temporal fluctuations in the tremor’s rhythmic signature could determine whether the stimulation
 319 successfully engages the central oscillator or remains sub-threshold.

320 Several limitations should be acknowledged. Firstly, although tSCS is primarily intended to engage afferent pathways,
 321 it may also recruit efferent fibers [34], especially when using a high frequency carrier [35]. However, stimulation
 322 intensities were carefully adjusted to remain below the threshold for direct motor responses. No visible muscle
 323 contractions or evoked responses were observed, nor were any stimulation-induced motor artifacts or unintended
 324 movements detected during active task performance. This suggests that the observed effects were likely mediated by
 325 the modulation of spinal excitability. TSCS limited spatial specificity could also have influenced motor units beyond
 326 the targeted muscle, potentially including muscles not directly involved in the task. Such unintended activation might
 327 have contributed to variability in the recorded tremor response, representing an intrinsic limitation of the technique that
 328 should be taken into account when interpreting the results. A further limitation is the absence of a sham-controlled,
 329 blinded comparator controlling for the possibility that tSCS could produce a perceptible tapping sensation phase-locked
 330 to the tremor cycle that could produce phase-dependent somatosensory, attentional, or expectancy effects. This should
 331 be explicitly tested in future sham-controlled trials. Also, the effects reported here are restricted to short stimulation
 332 blocks and to single experimental sessions with the patients. Additional studies are needed to test whether phase-specific
 333 tSCS could achieve sustained benefits with longer or repeated applications and if optimal phase alignments remain
 334 stable across sessions within subjects. Lastly, pulse width and carrier frequency were chosen based on previous reports
 335 [22]. While the intensity (90% MT) is coherent with established protocols, further optimization of these waveform
 336 parameters may be necessary. Precise tSCS [36] and SCS [37] parameter tuning is essential for clinical efficacy, so
 337 individualized configurations might improve tremor modulation depth in future iterations.

338 In conclusion, this study demonstrates that tSCS can modulate essential tremors in a phase-dependent manner. Our
 339 findings confirm the technical feasibility of a low-latency closed-loop framework capable of tracking tremor oscillations
 340 in real-time directly from EMG. Although the response depth varied across participants, the evidence of phase-specific
 341 modulation establishes the spinal cord as a non-invasive interface to engage central tremorgenic networks. This work
 342 provides a foundation for future personalized neuromodulation strategies that prioritize precise stimulation timing over
 343 continuous application.

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347 4.1 Figures

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